

CAUSES AND DIAGNOSIS OF INTRAUTERINE GROWTH RESTRICTION SYNDROME

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The article presents the results of a research causes leading to intrauterine growth restriction syndrome and its early diagnosis.

In this research 60 pregnant women between 21 and 38 years old were examined and studied their obstetrical, gynecological and somatic anamnesis. Also we carried out ultrasound examination in all pregnant women to evaluate the fetoplacental system. The main group consisted of 30 women with intrauterine growth restriction syndrome. The control group consisted of 30 conditionally healthy pregnant women.

Key words: intrauterine growth restriction syndrome, ultrasound examination, Doppler velocimetry, fetoplacental insufficiency.

Fetal growth restriction syndrome (FGRS) refers to the discrepancy between the fetal body weight and the average body weight for this period of pregnancy. The main number of newborns who have undergone to intrauterine growth restriction syndrome is found in Asia, followed by Africa and Latin America.[1].

Chronic inflammatory diseases of the urinary tract and female genital organs can lead to endothelial dysfunction due to the formation of cytokines and protein synthesis disorders. And as a result, these processes can lead to hypercoagulation and the development of FGRS[3,]. Prediction of fetal growth retardation based on clinical and anamnestic data. Fetal growth retardation is a multifactorial disease .In addition to ultrasound diagnostics, Dopplerometry is also an important diagnostic method. To date, a safe, highly diagnostic, rapidly conducted and economically affordable Doppler examination is the main method for assessing the state of uteroplacental circulation and fetal hemodynamics.[2,4,5]

The aim of the study is to study the causes of developing fetal growth retardation syndrome and its early diagnosis.

Materials and methods of research. To solve the tasks, carried out a prospective analysis of 60 pregnant women in the 2nd and 3rd trimester of gestation. The main group consisted of 30 pregnant women of developing FGRS at 28-38 weeks, the control group consisted of 30 conditionally healthy pregnant women at the time of the examination.

The results of the study and their discussion. According to the retrospective analysis, the average age of pregnant women in the retrospective analysis with FGRS was 28.5 ± 5.12 years (between 21 to 36 years). When analyzing the parity of the retrospective group, there were many patients with the first pregnancy and the first birth, 19 (63.3%) and 18 (63%), respectively, but the number of patients with repeated pregnancy, 11 (36.6%) and multi-pregnant also prevailed: 7 (23.3%).

According to studies, it was revealed that in pregnant women with FGRS, the anamnesis was burdened with various somatic diseases, the analysis of which showed sufficient variability in the frequency of various nosological forms. Anemia was most often noted (90% or more in both groups), ARVI was noted in 43% and varicose veins in 30%, which may be a full risk for the development of FGRS. When studying the obstetric history of women, it was noted that patients with FGRS had a history of hypertensive conditions 33.3% of cases ($p < 0.05$), threatening preterm labor 23.3% ($p < 0.05$), amniotic fluid discharge in 16.7% of cases ($p < 0.05$) and antenatal fetal death in previous pregnancies in 10% of pregnant women, ($p < 0.05$).

We also studied the gynecological history of the examined women. According to it, many pregnant women were previously observed and treated for various gynecological diseases. As follows from the diagrams presented, inflammatory diseases of the uterine appendages and ectopia of the cervix were most often detected. A high level of inflammatory diseases of the genital organs was observed in all groups, and in women with varicose veins more often than in patients with isolated dilation of the venous vessels of the pelvis. Thus, chronic inflammatory processes of the uterus and appendages in the anamnesis were detected in 37.8% of women.

Ultrasound examinations in dynamics were performed in 60 pregnant women of the main and control groups. Significant differences throughout the third trimester of pregnancy were revealed between the values of LV and DB in fetuses of patients of the main and control groups. Thus, the values of LV in the fetuses of pregnant women of the main group were lower than in the fetuses of patients of the control group at 36 weeks - by 7% and at 40 weeks - by 8%. The DB values in the fetuses of pregnant women of the main group were less than in the fetuses of patients of the control group at 36 weeks - by 3% and at 40 weeks - by 4%.

Conclusion.

According to the research, the most significant risk factors for the development of fetal growth restriction syndrome in pregnant women include anemia in 95% of cases, ARVI was noted in 43%, varicose veins in 30% of cases, chronic hypertension in 33% of cases, urinary tract infections in 4% of cases ($p>0.05$). At the same time, it was noted that in the burdened obstetric and gynecological history, the leading positions were occupied by such complications as: threatening miscarriages in 23.3% of cases ($p<0.05$), amniotic fluid discharge in 16.7% of cases ($p<0.05$) and antenatal fetal death in previous pregnancies in 10% of pregnant women ($p<0.05$), chronic inflammatory processes of the uterus and appendages in the anamnesis were detected in 34 (37.8%) women.

Thus, different degrees of hemodynamic disorders of placental circulation were observed in fetuses of patients of the main group with the same frequency. In the patients of the main group in the uterine arteries and umbilical cord arteries, vascular resistance indicators were higher than in pregnant women of the control group. Dopplerometric parameters of blood flow in the middle cerebral artery of pregnant fetuses of the main group were lower than similar parameters in pregnant women of the control group.

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